

PACIFICUS

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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“MY FIRSTBORN”

The first time you cried still lingers in my mind
A beautiful moment that brings me to cloud nine
Even my body chills, my heart is so warm
When I see you, my little one, everything is fine

In your eyes, a love so true
A bond between us, forever new
You, my little one, a treasure rare
A blessing to me, beyond compare

When I hold you, I see your smile
It melts my heart that makes me cry
I ask myself, "Is this real?"
Yes, I am now a mother of this little angel

As months go by, I see you grow
Time is so fast, I still want to hear your coo
Though you grow so fast and free
In my heart, you'll forever be my baby